

Programme

Online-Programme
with Abstracts

Venue (unless indicated otherwise):

Fritz Thyssen Foundation, Amélie Thyssen Auditorium, Apostelnkloster 13-15, 50672 Cologne

Wednesday, October 5th

14:00	Registration	
15:00 – 15:15	Welcome to the CAA Joint Chapter Meeting	
15:15 – 16:15	Lutz Schubert/Jürgen Landauer/Alex Brandsen <i>Panel on Artificial Intelligence in Archaeology</i>	
16:15 – 16:45	Coffee Break	
16:45 – 18:15	AGM of the CAA Germany - Amélie Thyssen Auditorium	AGM of the CAA NL/FL - Robert Ellscheid Hall
18:15	Welcome Reception in the foyer of the Fritz Thyssen Foundation	

Thursday, October 6th

8:15 - 9:00	Registration	
Managing and disseminating archaeological data		
9:00 - 9.30	Florian Thiery/Allard Mees <i>NAVIS ONE: Challenges and Opportunities for RSE and RDM by designing a common web application from a 1990s online database</i>	
9:30 – 10:00	Tijm Lanjouw/Jitte Waagen <i>3DWorkSpace – an open science/interactive tool for 3D datasets</i>	
10:00 – 10:30	Gunhilt Merker/Jana Nolle/Szymon Domagała <i>GIS - painlessly. Increasing the efficiency of archaeological documentation through simplification of geodata management and geoprocessing</i>	
10:30 – 11:00	Coffee Break	
Socio-ecological modelling		
11:00 – 11:30	Eleftheria Paliou/Oliver Vogels/Lucía Cobo-Sánchez/Tilman Lenssen-Erz <i>Indigenous knowledge and Archaeoinformatics: Tapping into Indigenous Knowledge to advance computational models of hunter-gatherer societies</i>	
11:30 – 12:00	Louise Tharandt/Vlad Krakov/Florian Linsel/Patrick Ludwig/Andreas Maier <i>Timing and length of vegetation periods as a potential driver for long-term trends in the movement and distribution of hunter-gatherer populations</i>	
12:00 – 12:30	Andreas Angourakis/Dries Daems/ Philip Verhagen <i>NASSA's open library of archaeological ABM modules: overview and examples</i>	
12:30 – 13:00	Jana Eger-Karberg/Tim Karberg <i>Reconstruction of ancient ecologically favoured zones in Western Sudan</i>	
13:00 – 14:30	Lunch Break	
Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning		
14:30 – 15:00	Alex Brandsen/Karsten Lambers/Suzan Verberne/Milco Wansleeben <i>Digging in Documents - Creating a Search Engine for Archaeological Literature using Text Mining</i>	
15:00 – 15:30	Alpheus Lien-Talks <i>Releasing the knowledge hidden in PDFs by using NLP and NER</i>	
15:30 – 16:00	Guilherme D'Andrea Curra <i>Classification of pottery assemblages in archaeology: a machine learning approach</i>	
16:00 – 16:30	Coffee Break	

Network Analysis	
16:30 – 17:00	Johanna Hilpert/Steffen Strohm/Tim Kerig <i>Interlinking Big Exchange – Exceptionally large raw material networks in prehistoric Europe and beyond</i>
17:00 – 17:30	Daria Stefan <i>Impact of Levantine transit trade on the cities of Transylvania, Wallachia and Moldova in the 17th century</i>
Spatial Analysis	
17:30 – 18:00	Bruno de Souza Barreto <i>Between Migration and Exchange: Addressing the Koriabo pottery and the late Carib-speaking expansions by means of Least-Cost-Path Analysis</i>
18:00 – 18:30	Irmela Herzog <i>Testing an approach for close-range visibility analysis</i>
19:00	Dinner at the Brauerei Paffgen, Friesenstraße 64-66, 50670 Cologne

Friday, October 7th

8:30 - 9:00	Registration
Archaeological Prospection	
9:00 – 9:30	Hendrik Rohland/Marco Block-Berlitz/Christina Franken <i>Large-Scale aerial surveys in Mongolia: Direct versus automated georeferencing methods</i>
9:30 – 10:00	R. Kniess/A. Fediuk/H. Zöllner/R. Freibothe/N. Allroggen/B. Ullrich <i>Application of various Ground-Penetrating Radar antenna systems and processing software on an archaeological test site</i>
10:00 – 10:30	Joep Orbons <i>Hof van Maarland: underground, in the air, in bits and bytes</i>
10:30 – 11:00	Coffee Break
11:00 – 11:30	Jitte Waagen <i>Geophysical, Aerial and Thermal Prospection at Magoula Plataniotiki</i>
11:30 – 12:00	Piotr Szczepanik/Radosław Palonka <i>Non-invasive approach to Ancient Pueblos: Results of geophysical surveys by Sand Canyon-Castle Rock Community Archaeological Project in Colorado, USA (2011-2019)</i>
Artefact documentation	
12:00 – 12:30	Priscilla Ulguim/Tim Thompson <i>Algorithmic Approaches for Visualising Heat-Induced Change in Burned Bones</i>
12:30 – 13:00	Markus Stoffer/Tijm Lanjouw <i>Interactive visualisation of volumetric CT data in a museum context: the animal mummies of the Allard Pierson</i>
13:00 – 14:30	Lunch Break
Engaging the public	
14:30 – 15:00	L. Loges/S. Döpfer/M. Ludwig/I. Gurjanow/D-X. Ken Oehler <i>Digital Public Archaeology with the ArchaeoTrail App</i>
15:00 – 15:30	Matheus Morais Cruz <i>Archaeology and digital games/simulations: a cyber-archaeological VR prototype about the Vetera I legionary camp</i>
15:30 – 16:00	Manuel Palacio <i>Memories from a digital city: Use of Archaeogaming on “Pasajeros”, a Colombian videogame</i>
16:00 – 16:10	Louise Tharandt <i>From previous on-site reconstructions to current virtual 3D reconstructions - A look at the impact of recreating the past using the example of the megalithic tomb Düwelsteene in Westphalia</i>
17:00 – 20:00	Excursions / Visits Information about the excursions will be provided during the conference